

EVALUATING THE ECONOMIC GROWTH IMPLICATIONS OF REVENUE GENERATION IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study centred on investigating the impact of revenue generation on the economic growth in Nigeria using annual time series data which covered the period of 2013 – 2022. These relationships were estimated with the autoregressive distributed lag model (ARDL) and the findings were robustly checked with the fully modified ordinary least squares (FMOLS). The findings from the ARDL results reveal that while tax revenue has a positive and significant impact on economic growth, value-added tax showed an insignificant impact, while customs and other import duties showed a significant negative influence on economic growth in Nigeria. From the FMOLS results, we found that revenue generation indicators – tax revenue, value-added tax and customs and other import duties have significant negative effects on economic growth. Improving revenue generation in Nigeria requires a multifaceted approach that encompasses tax reform, regional strategies, human capital development, and environmental sustainability initiatives. By adopting these measures, Nigeria can create a more diversified economy that not only generates sufficient revenue but also provides a solid foundation for sustainable economic growth and development. Future research should continue to explore innovative revenue generation strategies and their direct impact on Nigeria's economic landscape to guide policymakers in their efforts to build a resilient economy.

Keywords: Economic Growth, Revenue Generation, Nigeria.

1. INTRODUCTION

Economic growth is vital for Nigeria's development and prosperity, serving as a key indicator of the economy's health. When the economy grows, businesses expand, investments increase, and job opportunities multiply, leading to higher incomes and improved living standards (Onuchukwu, Kalagbor & Nzor, 2012). Strong economic growth also boosts national income, enabling the government to invest more in essential public services such as healthcare, education, and infrastructure. This not only enhances the quality of life for citizens but also drives higher production and labour demand. A thriving economy increases government revenue through taxes and other public income streams (Abu & Abdullahi, 2010). It also

attracts foreign direct investment (FDI), which is crucial for economic diversification and development. Additionally, robust growth helps reduce public debt by improving government revenues and lowering the need for external borrowing. It strengthens Nigeria's global competitiveness and supports infrastructure development essential for sustained economic activity (Tyagi, 2013). However, without effective revenue generation, achieving consistent economic growth remains challenging. Ensuring fair and efficient revenue generation is fundamental to financing critical sectors and sustaining Nigeria's long-term growth. Revenue generation plays a pivotal role in shaping the economic growth of Nigeria, a country heavily reliant on its natural resources, particularly oil, but striving for diversification and sustainable development. The relationship between revenue generation and economic growth is both direct and multifaceted, influencing various sectors and government functions (Manasseh et al. 2022).

Revenue generation provides the government with the financial resources necessary to invest in infrastructural projects, such as roads, bridges, power supply, and telecommunications. These infrastructures are essential for enhancing the productivity of various sectors, reducing production costs, and increasing the efficiency of businesses (Garga & Akanegbu 2022). Furthermore, revenue generation influences economic growth by funding public services such as education, healthcare, and social welfare, and helps reduce fiscal deficits and reliance on external borrowing (Onoja & Ibrahim). Therefore, strategic ways of generating revenue are required to foster economic growth in Nigeria. Control should be placed by the authorities by reducing fiscal deficits, stimulating private sector growth, enhancing security, and effective revenue generation which supports the foundations of a thriving economy.

From the above discussion, it is clear that revenue generation plays a crucial role in driving economic growth in Nigeria. One of its primary functions is to fund essential public services such as healthcare, education, and social security. When revenue generation is effective, governments can provide quality services that improve living standards and foster human capital development. For example, investing in education helps build a skilled workforce, while healthcare spending ensures a healthier and more productive population. This study examines how revenue generation — measured by tax revenue (% of GDP), value-added tax (VAT), and customs and other import duties — impacts Nigeria's economic growth. To explore this, we sought to answer three key research questions: (a) Does tax revenue significantly influence economic growth in Nigeria? (b) What is the impact of value-added tax on Nigeria's economic growth? and, (c) How do customs and import duties affect Nigeria's economic growth? To address these questions, we applied the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model, complemented by fully modified ordinary least squares (FMOLS) for robustness. This approach provided comprehensive insights into how revenue generation affects economic growth in Nigeria.

This study stands out from existing research in several key ways. First, we focused on the impact of tax revenue on economic growth in Nigeria, recognizing its critical role in providing the financial resources needed for infrastructure development, public services, and economic diversification. By reducing over-reliance on oil revenue, effective taxation promotes fiscal sustainability, supports national security, and enhances the overall stability and resilience of

the Nigerian economy. Secondly, we examined the impact of Value-Added Tax (VAT) on economic growth, given its significance as a stable revenue source for the Nigerian government. Nigeria's heavy dependence on oil revenue has left the economy vulnerable to global oil price fluctuations. VAT offers a more reliable alternative by taxing consumption across sectors like retail, manufacturing, and services. This broad-based approach captures revenue from the growing non-oil sectors, promoting economic diversification and resilience. VAT also encourages responsible consumption, as individuals and businesses are taxed based on purchases, discouraging wasteful spending and fostering prudent financial decision-making. Additionally, VAT provides steady funding for public investment, supports fiscal stability, and contributes to long-term development. Its role in formalizing businesses, reducing income inequality, and strengthening local government finances makes it a vital tool for fostering inclusive and sustainable economic growth in Nigeria.

We also explored the impact of customs and other import duties on Nigeria's economic growth, recognizing their dual role as a vital source of government revenue and a tool for protecting domestic industries. By encouraging local production, reducing trade imbalances, and supporting industrial growth, customs duties contribute to job creation and infrastructure development. When effectively managed and reinvested, this revenue can drive sustainable and inclusive economic growth in Nigeria.

To analyze these relationships, we employed the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model as our baseline approach due to its ability to capture both long-run and short-run dynamics simultaneously. To ensure robustness, we validated our findings using the Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS) method, which addresses endogeneity issues and accounts for potential unobserved shocks, including spatial effects. The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides a review of the literature, Section 3 outlines the methodology, Section 4 presents the empirical results and findings, and Section 5 offers conclusions and policy recommendations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Conceptual Framework

Achieving economic growth in Nigeria requires strong revenue generation from all sectors of the economy as a backup for government expenditure. Hence, effective revenue generation is vital for funding public services, promoting economic development, and ensuring fiscal stability. However, challenges such as corruption, a large informal economy, and overdependence on oil revenue hinder progress. Implementing comprehensive tax reforms, strengthening institutions, enhancing public awareness, and diversifying revenue sources are crucial strategies for improving revenue generation in Nigeria. This study conceptualized the impact of revenue generation on economic growth in Nigeria in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of the impact of revenue generation on economic growth in Nigeria

Source: Authors' Concept.

2.2. Theoretical Literature

One of the theories used in explaining the concept and impact of government revenue as well as expenditure on the economy is the theory of John Maynard Keynes, whose classical theory developed in 1933 in the heat of the great depression that hit the Western world economies has continued to generate debates amongst scholars and economist in particular. Keynesian theory states that the government through its fiscal policy can influence macroeconomic productivity levels by increasing or decreasing tax levels (revenue levels) and public spending (public expenditure). It further argued that this influence was created as a result of manipulating those variables in turn reducing inflation, increasing employment and also maintaining a good value for money. He in other words believed that fiscal policy intervention will lead to a countercyclical measure and when the market forces are left alone, they lead to a stable level of economy where underemployment is seen at the equilibrium (Tyagi, 2013). Their central belief is that public finance and expenditure when adequately combined can help governments achieve their macroeconomic objectives that put them on the path of growth and development. It further suggests that governments can increase revenue and expenditure as the case may be to achieve their economic objectives (Onuchukwu, Kalagbor & Nzor, 2012). In other words, if expenditure is increased for instance, production and investment activities could be stirred up in the economy thereby making the productive sector to be active which can be seen in terms of job creation opportunities and income flow. In addition, production will trigger exports and thus increase exports and reduce on imports. Similarly, when revenue is increased expenditure should also increase at the same time otherwise a deficit situation could occur thus putting the actualization of macroeconomic objectives in jeopardy.

As Abu and Abdullahi (2010) argued, within the Keynesian model, when the government increases spending, it leads to higher economic growth and vice versa. This is done by way of keeping an equilibrium between effective demand and supply of goods and services, through the manipulation of revenue and expenditure by the government. However, this spending that is needed to spur this economic level of stability is the spending that is geared towards increasing the productive sector of the economy. Other spending that is not tailored towards

these will not yield the desired result in terms of the macroeconomic objectives. Having highlighted this theory as it relates to government revenue and economic development, this study however anchors on Keynesian theory as it concurs with the theory of public finance. The underlying principle as it pertains to public expenditure and revenue as this theory posits is to put policies that will enable the government to generate the needed revenue for the nation and then channel these to the economy in such a way that economic growth and development can be attained.

2.3. Empirical Literature

The dynamic relationship between tax revenue, infrastructural development and economic growth in Nigeria was examined by Ayeni and Afolabi (2020) using time series data covering the period from 1981 to 2018. Vector autoregression (VAR) and other robust estimation tools were employed and the study found that while tax revenue influences economic growth and infrastructure, infrastructure on the other hand does not influence economic growth, though it significantly impacts tax revenue collected. In the same year, Onoja and Ibrahim (2020) investigated Tax Revenue (PPT, VAT and CIT) and Nigeria's Economic Growth. Secondary data collected were analyzed with regression analysis and the study affirmed no significant but positive relationship between economic growth and Petroleum Profit Tax. While Value Added Tax and Companies Income Tax (non-oil Tax Revenue) revealed a significant relationship with Nigeria's Economic Growth. Subsequently, Olushlola, et al. (2020) assessed tax revenue and economic growth with an econometric approach. Secondary data was employed and analyzed using a multiple regression model and the result suggested a positive relationship between tax revenue and economic growth. Furthermore, in the work of Ewa, et al. (2020), the impact of taxation proceeds (company profits, petroleum profit and value-added tax) on the development of the Nigerian economy covering a period from 1994 to 2018 was determined. The study adopted Ordinary Least Square and found a significant effect of CIT and Value Added Tax on Gross Domestic Product Growth, Petroleum profit tax has little or no effect on Gross Domestic Product growth in Nigeria. In a recent work by Anisere-Hameed (2021), the impact of taxation (PPT, CGT and CIT) on the growth and development of the Nigerian economy was examined.

Data was obtained and analyzed via the Ordinary least square (OLS) regression method and the result showed CGT and PPT as insignificant towards the economic growth of Nigeria. Whereas CIT has a significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria. Similarly, Yaro and Adeiza (2021) investigated the relationship between taxation and economic growth in Nigeria. A simple percentage method was used and the results revealed a positive significant impact of both non-oil revenue and profit tax on the growth of Nigeria. Nwachukwu, et al. (2022), examined the effect of taxation on economic growth in Nigeria. Secondary data was gathered and analyzed using OLS and other inferential tools. The results reveal that PPT, VAT, CIT and PIT have a positive and significant effect on the economic growth parameters. Nwobodo, et al. (2022) examined indirect taxes and the economic growth of Nigeria. The study gathered secondary data on VAT, CED and GDP, using ARDL; the study found that VAT and CED influence GDP positively. Ihenyen and Ogbise, (2022) examined the effect of tax revenue generation on economic growth in Nigeria. Secondary data was obtained from reliable sources,

using multiple linear regression, the study found that PPT, CIT and VAT have a positive impact on Nigeria's economic growth while customs and excise duties hurt Nigeria's economic growth. Etim et al. (2021) used a descriptive and inferential statistical technique, correlational and regression statistics, and an ex post facto research design, study to compare the effects of direct and indirect taxation on the growth of the Nigerian economy. The study demonstrated that indirect taxes have a greater detrimental impact on economic growth. Mukolu and Ogodor's (2021) study examined the impact of VAT on Nigerian economic growth for the year 1994 to 2018 using an Augmented Dickey-Fuller analysis method. Data was obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin and the Federal Inland Revenue Service. The study showed that there is a positively significant impact of Value Added Tax on Gross Domestic Product. It also showed that VAT has to a great extent given rise to the total revenue of the nation and has helped in tax evasion by taxpayers.

John and Dickson (2020) using Error Correction Models analyzed the influence of tax revenue on economic growth using both unadjusted and adjusted Gross Domestic Product from 1984 to 2018. When GDP was not adjusted for inflation, PPT had a minor but beneficial effect on economic growth, whereas VAT and CIT had a large but negative impact on GDP. PPT had a negative and insignificant impact on adjusted GDP, but VAT had a positive and considerable impact, and CIT had a negative and significant one. Yadawananda and Achal (2020) investigated the long-run and short-run relationship between tax structure and state-level growth performance for the years 1991 to 2016 using the panel regression method. The findings revealed that commodity and service taxes were bad for the economy and an increase in those taxes would lead to inflation while income taxes were found to be significant for the economy as it mostly impacts the savings and labour supply which is regarded as the drive for economic growth. Adeusi et al. (2020) investigated the impact of non-oil revenue on the economic growth of Nigeria where company income tax, value-added tax, personal income tax and custom and excise duties where the non-oil revenue for the period 1994–2018 with data obtained from Federal Inland Revenue Service and National Bureau of Statistics. Ordinary Least Square Regression Techniques were used for data analysis. The study revealed that Value Added Tax and Custom and Excise duties have a more significant positive impact on economic growth while Company Income Tax and Personal Income Tax have a negative but significant effect on economic growth. In their study, Johansson, Heady, Arnold, Brys, and Vartia (2020) examined the relationship between tax and economic growth. Their work argued that revenue generated from tax channels is meant for public services. This simultaneously affects household savings and investment reactions, human development, employment rates, and investment channels and assets portfolio. With a focus on OECD countries, the study centred on the effect of tax structure changes on GDP per capita and the effecting determinants thereof. The study was limited to the dilemma of examining how much impact tax structures had on GDP levels or growth as long-term effects on GDP levels are purely theoretical.

It reiterated the importance of eliminating tax burdens on taxpayers (optimal taxation), costs of tax reform transitions, and practical experiences of OECD member countries Egolum and Celestine (2021) ascertained the effect of value-added tax on economic development in Nigeria from 1994-2018. Two hypotheses were formulated in line with the objective of the study. Time

series research design was adopted and the data for the study were obtained from the CBN statistical bulletin, Federal Inland Revenue bulletin and Joint Tax Board bulletin for the period under study. Pearson coefficient of correlation and simple regression analysis were applied for the test of the hypotheses formulated with the aid of EViews 9.0 statistical software. Findings showed that Value Added Tax had a positive and statistically significant relationship with economic development (proxied by Gross Domestic Product and Total Government Revenue) at 5% significant level. Based on these findings, the study recommends among others that Government should therefore put in place measures to enhance productivity so as to increase the contribution of VAT to economic growth and development in Nigeria. Monica and Kazeem (2022) examined the effect of VAT on economic growth in Nigeria between 1994 and 2020 using the consumer price index (CPI) as a threshold. A technique of Threshold Vector Autoregressive (TVAR) was employed and the results reveal that a VAT above the 10 per cent threshold value endangers the economy while a VAT below the 7.59 per cent threshold value does not harm the economy; rather, it improves people's well-being. It is therefore recommended that the Nigerian economy should maintain the lower VAT threshold to cushion the effect of ever-rising CPI on the citizens.

Also, Agunbiade and Idebi (2020) studied tax revenue and economic growth in Nigeria for a period of 38 years (1981–2019). Companies Income Tax, Value Added Tax and Petroleum Profits Tax were the variables of interest. Having analyzed the data using the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) and other post-estimation tools the study documented a causal relationship between Real GDP and the tax components. The result also showed that the direct tax (CIT and PPT) effect on GDP was low, whereas the indirect tax (VAT) effect on GDP is significantly increased over the period. Maganya (2020) examine the impact of taxation on economic growth in Tanzania by employing the recently developed autoregressive distributed lag model (ARDL) bounds testing procedure for the period spanning from 1996 to 2019. The findings reveal that domestic goods and services (TGS) taxes exhibit a positive relationship with GDP growth and are statistically significant at a 1% level. Conversely, income taxes demonstrate a negative association with GDP growth and are statistically significant at a 5% level. The pairwise Granger causality results indicate the presence of bidirectional causality between TGS and GDP growth at a 1% significance level. Dumisani Pamba (2022) investigated the relationship between different components of tax revenue and economic growth in South Africa. The study utilized time series data spanning over 22 years. The stationarity of the variables was determined using the Phillips-Perron (PP) unit root test, and the existence of both long-run and short-run equilibrium conditions was examined using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model. The results show all variables were found to be cointegrated, indicating a long-run relationship with economic growth. The ARDL findings indicated that company income tax, personal income tax, and taxes on international trade and transactions have a positive long-run and short-run association with economic growth. On the other hand, capital gain tax, foreign direct investment, and gross savings have a negative long-run and short-run relationship with economic growth.

Kessy and Sukartini (2023) evaluate the impact of taxation on economic growth specifically in Africa. Spanning a period of eleven years, from 2008 to 2018, the study incorporates multiple

variables from 21 African countries. Gross Domestic Product (GDP) serves as the dependent variable, serving as a proxy for economic growth. Independent variables encompass a range of factors that influence GDP, categorized into three groups: the supply side, which includes human capital (population and literacy rate) and economic activities (trade and services); the demand side, which includes variables such as consumption, government expenditures, net exports, and gross capital formation; and lastly, taxation variables, which encompass tax revenue, corporate tax rate, number of tax payments, personal income tax, and taxes on income, profits, and capital gains. Tax revenue and corporate tax rate demonstrate a positive impact on GDP, while personal income tax rate and taxes on income, profits, and capital gains exhibit a negative influence on GDP. Overall, taxation appears to have a beneficial effect on the economies of African countries, as emerging nations utilize taxation as an internal mechanism to generate revenue and enhance economic growth. Abiola et al. (2021) conducted a causal-effect study on tax revenue, capital formation, and economic growth, revealing the significant positive impact of tax revenue on GDP. The study proposed widening the tax net and implementing expansionary measures to enhance tax revenue and boost GDP. Also, Edori (2022) analysed the impact of tax revenue, specifically corporate income tax, VAT, and petroleum profit tax, on Nigeria's economic growth. The study revealed a positive but insignificant relationship between the variables, attributing the insignificance to poor tax revenue management. The recommendation emphasized the efficient and effective utilization of tax revenue for infrastructure development. Additionally, Onoja and Ibrahim (2020) focused on the analysis of tax revenue's impact on Nigeria's economic growth. The study found a positive but not significant relationship between petroleum profit tax (oil tax revenue) and economic growth, while VAT and companies' income tax (non-oil tax revenue) had significant relationships. The study recommended minimizing corruption in tax administration, transparently accounting for tax revenue, and supporting entrepreneurial activities.

In the same vein, Amah (2021) examined the effect of the taxation system on the Nigerian economy from 1999 to 2017. The study revealed a significant positive relationship between GDP and PPT as well as CIT. The study recommended the provision of an enabling environment for companies to generate more revenue in addition to the reduction in the VAT rate to encourage consumption. Garga and Akanegbu (2022) analysed the impact of direct tax on Nigeria's economic growth, finding a positive impact of CIT on economic growth. The study concluded that both CIT and PPT had positive impacts on the economic growth of Nigeria. This empirical literature provides a robust framework for exploring the multifaceted dimensions of taxation in shaping economic policies. Bello (2022) used Kwara state in Nigeria as a case study to gain a better understanding of the many revenue streams in Nigeria that are not derived from oil.

Through the utilization of the Relative Importance Index (RII) and the chi-square independent test, the study was able to separate the effects of the difficulties in earning non-oil revenues from the significance of the factors that lie beneath those difficulties. According to the findings, Customs and Excise Duties as well as Companies' Income Tax are the most important non-oil income-producing sources based on the difficulties that are experienced. Akpa et al. (2022) investigated Nigeria's non-oil export revenues as well as the country's GDP growth. The data

were examined using a retrospective perspective in the study. To investigate the connection between GDP and NOEXP, a technique known as ordinary least squares (OLS) analysis was carried out. NOEXP was found to have a positive impact on GDP growth in Nigeria and was identified by researchers based on statistical analysis.

In their study, Oboro and Aguwamba (2022) disaggregate the data to assess the degree to which non-oil exports have played a role in the expansion of Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) between the years 1990 and 2020. The methodology used in this research was the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) technique. The findings of the study indicated that non-oil export indicators have a much greater influence on economic growth compared to agriculture and industrial exports. Wadike, et al., (2022) analyzed Nigerian data to examine the potential correlation between an increase in gross domestic product (GDP) and a corresponding increase in non-oil tax income. The period included the years 1985 to 2017.

The magnitude of the associations between the variables was determined via the use of the ordinary least squares methodology. The findings indicated that corporate income tax positively influences GDP, however, income tax does not have any impact on GDP. Henry (2021) researched to investigate how oil and non-oil revenue influence the expansion of Nigeria's economy. This analysis covers thirty-five years, beginning in 1981 and ending in 2015.

The data showed that earnings from oil and non-oil had a significant and beneficial effect on GDP. Similarly, Olurankinse and Fatukasi (2020) used the ordinary least squares (OLS) approach to investigate the influence that non-oil industries have on the expansion of the GDP. During the research, it was determined that non-oil-related revenue was the primary contributor to the expansion of the Nigerian economy. They however decry the below-average performance in terms of the revenue mobilization and output level of non-oil revenue which they felt is abysmal and below expectation.

They recommended among other things that Nigeria need a paradigm shift from the primitive reliance on oil and gas to a more expanded and sustainable non-oil revenue base. Olufemi (2020), investigated the impact of taxation on Nigeria's economic growth between 1980 and 2019. The study employed the Vector Error Correction Model and Granger Causality estimation technique to analyze the data. The study found that personal income tax and value-added tax had a positive impact on the economic growth of Nigeria.

Ogbonna (2021) researched the impact of non-oil revenue and economic growth in Nigeria between 1981 and 2019. The study employed the ARDL model to examine the impact and the result showed that non-oil revenue has a positive and significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria. Yusuf et al. (2021) researched the dynamic impact of VAT on economic growth in Nigeria between 1994 and 2019. The study utilized the dynamic ordinary least square method to examine the impact and the result showed that VAT has a positive relationship with economic growth in Nigeria. Ideh et al. (2021) empirically examined the impact of non-oil sector revenue on economic growth in Nigeria from 2000 to 2019. The vector autoregressive method was employed and it revealed that the revenues generated by sectors categorized under non-oil

contributed to the growth of Nigeria's economy between 2000 and 2019. Fossong et al. (2021) empirically analyzed the effect of oil and non-oil revenue on economic growth in Cameroon from 1980 to 2018. The study employed the ARDL method of analysis and the result revealed that non-oil revenue exerts a negative but significant impact on economic growth in the long run while in the short run, it is positive and statistically significant.

Nedra and Kavita (2020) also examined the impact of non-oil revenue on the economy of Saudi Arabia for the period of 1994 to 2019, using descriptive statistics and correlation analysis. The findings showed that non-oil revenue (VAT, CIT, and PIT) exerts a positive and industrial impact on economic growth in Saudi Arabia. Owusu and Olabisi (2020) studied the impact of non-oil revenue on economic growth in Nigeria from 2011 to 2016. The study utilized a fully modified ordinary least square method and the result showed that non-oil revenue impacts negatively on economic growth in Nigeria.

Olowo et al. (2020) studied the impact of non-oil revenue on economic growth in Nigeria between 1981 and 2018, using the ARDL model. The findings revealed that the sectoral distribution of non-oil revenue is positive and significant to economic growth in Nigeria. Raja and Assil (2020) studied the impact of non-oil revenue on economic growth in Saudi Arabia from the period of 1990 to 2018, using the ordinary least square method. It was revealed from the study that non-oil revenue has negative effects on economic growth in the study area.

Ilori and Akinwumi (2020) examined the effect of oil and non-oil revenue on economic growth in Nigeria. The study covered the period from 1989 to 2018 and utilized an error correction mechanism to examine the effect. The findings showed that oil and non-oil revenue harms real gross domestic product in Nigeria. Alexander et al. (2019) also utilized the ARDL model to study the impact of taxation on economic growth in Nigeria between 1980 and 2018. The result showed that petroleum profit tax, personal income tax and value-added tax have significant effects on the economic growth process in Nigeria.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Data Definitions and Sources

This study explores how revenue generation affects economic growth in Nigeria over a 12-year period (2010 to 2022). The choice of variables was guided by an extensive review of existing literature to ensure relevance and robustness. Economic growth is measured using real gross domestic product (RGDP), while revenue generation is captured through key indicators such as tax revenue (TAX), value-added tax (VAT), and customs and other import duties (COID). To account for other influencing factors, we included inflation rate (INFR) and interest rate (INTR) as control variables.

All data were obtained from the World Bank Development Indicators (WDI) to ensure reliability. For better clarity, Table 1 provides detailed definitions of each variable, along with their sources and repositories. This structured approach helps offer deeper insights into the relationship between revenue generation and economic growth in Nigeria.

Table 1: Definition of Data

Acronym	Definition	Repository	Source
RGDP	Real Gross Domestic Product – ratio of nominal GDP and GDP deflator	https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.MKTP.CD https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.DEFL.ZS	WDI
TAX	Tax revenue (% of GDP)	https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/GC.TAX.TOTL.GD.ZS	WDI
VAT	Value-Added Tax	https://www.firs.gov.ng/tax-resources-statistics	FIRS
COID	Customs and Other Import Duties	https://databank.worldbank.org/metadataglossary/world-development-indicators/series/GC.TAX.IMPT.CN	WDI
INFR	Inflation, consumer prices (annual %)	https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/FP.CPI.TOTL.ZG	WDI
INTR	Real interest rate (%)	https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/FR.INR.RINR	WDI

Source: Authors' Concept

3.2. Method of Data Analysis

3.2.1 Baseline Model – Panel ARDL (p, ..., q)

This study builds on the work of Manasseh et al. (2017, 2025) by using the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model as the baseline approach to examine how revenue generation impacts economic growth in Nigeria. The ARDL model stands out due to its flexibility and unique advantages over other cointegration techniques. While methods like the maximum likelihood-based Johansen (1991), the residual-based Engle and Granger (1987), and the Johansen and Juselius (1990) tests have been widely used in econometric research, they come with certain limitations. Manasseh et al. (2025) preferred the panel-based ARDL model because it allows variables to be integrated at different orders — whether I(0) or I(1) — without losing reliability (Pesaran et al., 2001). Moreover, the ARDL model generates an error correction model (ECM) through linear transformation (Banerjee et al., 1993), making it ideal for capturing both short- and long-run relationships. It is also suitable for small or finite sample sizes (Ghatak & Siddiki, 2001) and effectively addresses serial correlation and endogeneity issues (Pesaran et al., 2001). These strengths make it the ideal choice for this study. The empirical ARDL model is outlined below.

$$\Delta \ln RGDP_{it} = \omega_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \omega_1 \Delta \ln RGDP_{it-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \omega_2 \Delta \ln TAX_{it} + \sum_{i=1}^n \omega_3 \Delta \ln VAT_{it} + \sum_{i=1}^n \omega_4 \Delta \ln COID_{it} + \sum_{i=1}^n \omega_5 \Delta \ln INFR_{it} + \sum_{i=1}^n \omega_6 \Delta \ln INTR_{it} + \vartheta_1 \ln RGDP_{it} + \vartheta_2 \ln TAX_{it} + \vartheta_3 \ln VAT_{it} + \vartheta_4 \ln COID_{it} + \vartheta_5 \ln INFR_{it} + \vartheta_6 \ln INTR_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

Where: RGDP is the economic growth measure and the dependent variable, TAX is tax revenue, VAT is value-added tax, COID is custom and other import duties, INFR is the inflation rate, and INTR is the interest rate. Furthermore, ω_0 is the constant, ω_1 to ω_6 represents the coefficients of the long-run impacts, ϑ_1 to ϑ_6 , is the coefficients of the short-run dynamics, Δ , is the first difference operator, and \ln is the natural logarithm, while ε_{it} is the white noise error term. However, if the F-statistic lies above the upper-bound critical value for a given significance level, the conclusion is that there is a non-spurious long-run level relationship with

the dependent variable. If the F-statistic lies below the lower bound critical value, the conclusion is that there is no long-run level relationship with the dependent variable. If it lies between the lower and the upper limits, the result is inconclusive. The general form of the null and alternative hypotheses for the F-statistic test is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} H_0: & \vartheta_1 = \vartheta_2 = \vartheta_3 = \vartheta_4 = \vartheta_5 = \vartheta_6 = 0 \\ H_1: & \vartheta_1 \neq \vartheta_2 \neq \vartheta_3 \neq \vartheta_4 \neq \vartheta_5 \neq \vartheta_6 \neq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

If the cointegration between variables is identified, then one can undertake further analysis of the long-run and short-run (error correction) relationship between the variables. The error correction representation of the series can be specified as follows:

$$\Delta \ln RGDP_{it} = \omega_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \omega_1 \Delta \ln RGDP_{it-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \omega_2 \Delta \ln TAX_{it} + \sum_{i=1}^n \omega_3 \Delta \ln VAT_{it} + \sum_{i=1}^n \omega_4 \Delta \ln COID_{it} + \sum_{i=1}^n \omega_5 \Delta \ln INFR_{it} + \sum_{i=1}^n \omega_6 \Delta \ln INTR_{it} + \emptyset ECT + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (3)$$

Where ϑ the speed of adjustment parameter and ECT is the error correction term (the residuals obtained from equation 1). The coefficient of the lagged error correction term \emptyset is expected to be negative and statistically significant to further confirm the existence of a cointegrating relationship between the variables.

3.2.2. Robustness Check – FMOLS

To ensure the robustness of our results from the ARDL model, we conducted additional analysis using the panel Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS) method, following Manasseh et al. (2024) and building on the work of McCoskey and Kao (1998), Chiang (2000), Phillips & Moon (1999), and Pedroni (2000). The FMOLS approach effectively addresses cross-sectional dependency, country-specific differences, and heterogeneity issues. It provides optimal, consistent estimates of cointegration parameters, even in small samples, while tackling problems such as endogeneity, serial correlation, omitted variable bias, and measurement errors. One key advantage of FMOLS is its ability to accommodate heterogeneity in long-run parameters and correct for the correlation between the cointegrating equation and stochastic regressor innovations. The resulting FMOLS estimator is asymptotically unbiased and fully efficient, allowing for standard Wald tests using asymptotic Chi-square statistical inference. Additionally, it employs long-run covariance matrices of the residuals and can be estimated directly from difference regressions. The FMOLS model is specified as follows:

$$\beta^* NT - \beta FMOLS = \left[\sum_{i=1}^N L_{22t}^{-1} \sum_{t=1}^T (x_{it} - x_{it})^2 \right] \sum_{t=1}^N L_{11t}^{-1} L_{22t}^{-1} \left[\left(\sum_{t=1}^T (x_{it} - x_t) \mu_{it}^* - T_{\gamma 1} \right) \right] \quad (4)$$

4. EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this section, we examined how revenue generation affects economic growth in Nigeria using the ARDL model, with further validation through the Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS) technique. Before running the ARDL estimations, we conducted several essential econometric tests to ensure model reliability. These included normality tests, serial correlation

tests, the Ramsey model specification test, heteroscedasticity tests, unit root tests, and descriptive statistics. Revenue generation was measured using key indicators such as tax revenue, value-added tax (VAT), and customs and other import duties, based on the availability of annual data in Nigeria. Our analysis focused on interpreting the regression results obtained from secondary data collected for this study. This approach provided valuable insights into the relationship between revenue generation and economic growth, offering a robust understanding of how different revenue streams contribute to Nigeria’s economic performance.

4.1. Descriptive Statistics

We analyzed the overall behavior of the variables using descriptive statistics for the annual dataset spanning 2010 to 2022. Descriptive statistics provide a summary of key statistical measures, including the mean, median, minimum, maximum, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis. These metrics help to capture and summarize the essential features of the data. Table 3 presents the results of the descriptive statistics. The findings show that the mean, median, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis values are relatively consistent, indicating minimal variation across the dataset. Additionally, the probability values of most Jarque-Bera statistics are below 0.05, suggesting that the variables follow a normal distribution. This confirms their suitability for analyzing the relationships being tested in this study. Understanding these statistical properties is crucial for ensuring the reliability and validity of our econometric analysis.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics Results

	RGDP	TAX	VAT	COID	INFR	INTR
Mean	103.4	2.072	5.376	5.210	1.164	0.934
Median	124.5	2.080	0.899	5.136	1.053	0.805
Maximum	1.628	2.130	9.762	1.256	4.773	4.751
Minimum	5.001	2.010	0.313	0.694	-3.725	-2.641
Std. Dev.	42.52	0.043	20.34	2.811	1.346	1.581
Skewness	-0.034	0.104	4.252	0.379	0.204	0.325
Kurtosis	1.158	1.692	19.10	2.449	3.419	2.504
Jarque-Bera	5.943	3.060	580.3	1.538	10.01	19.96
Probability	0.051	0.216	0.000	0.463	0.006	0.000
Observations	12	12	12	12	12	12

Source: Authors’ Concept

4.2. Correlation Test

We furthered analysis by estimating the correlation analysis of the model variables to examine if there is existence of correlations between revenue generation and economic growth in Nigeria or not. Spearman’s correlation matrix measures the degree of linear relationship between each of the pair of variables in the model, and correlation values are ranked between -1 and +1. The larger the absolute value of the coefficient, the stronger the relationship between the variables, likewise, the lower the absolute values, the weaker the relationship between the variables (Gujarati, 2003). Also, according to Cohen (1988), the coefficients of the correlation will be reported based on the following rule of thumb: Strong relationship ± 5 , Moderate

relationship ± 3 and weak relationship ± 1 . Thus, below in Table 4 are the results of the Spearman's correlation test. Findings shows that tax revenue (TAX) have moderate negative correlations with economic growth, while value-added tax (VAT) has strong positive correlations with economic growth, but customs and other import duties (COID) has moderate correlations on economic growth, while inflation rate (INFR) and interest rate (INTR) have weak negative correlations with economic growth in Nigeria.

Table 2: Spearman's Correlation Test Results

	RGDP	TAX	VAT	COID	INFR	INTR
RGDP	1					
TAX	-0.619	1				
VAT	0.850	-0.699	1			
COID	0.528	-0.438	0.592	1		
INFR	-0.422	0.381	-0.427	-0.242	1	
INTR	-0.291	0.222	-0.232	-0.143	0.502	1

Source: Authors' Concept

4.3. Unit Root Test

We employed various unit root tests like Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test and Philips-Perron (PP) tests to ascertain the stationarity power of the variables and their order of integration and the results are presented in Table 3. The tests are guided by the null hypothesis "unit root" and alternative hypothesis "no unit root" and decision rule "reject the null hypothesis if the probability value is less than 0.05". The results shows that there is no trace of unit root in the series because the probability values of the variables in both ADF and PP tests are less than 0.05. Furthermore, the results also revealed that while some of the variables are integrated at level, others are integrated at first difference and no variable was found to be integrated at second-order i.e. I(2) and above. This therefore implied that the variables are suitable for the estimation of the ARDL analysis.

Table 3: Unit Root Tests Results

VARIABLE	ADF	Level	First Diff.	PP	Level	First Diff.
RGDP	-6.376*** (0.000)	I(0)	-	-6.376*** (0.000)	I(0)	-
TAX	-7.371*** (0.000)	I(0)	-	-7.563*** (0.000)	I(0)	-
VAT	-6.664*** (0.000)	-	I(1)	-3.021** (0.041)	I(0)	-
COID	-8.294*** (0.000)	-	I(1)	-8.074*** (0.000)	-	I(1)
INFR	-6.662*** (0.000)	-	I(1)	-6.880*** (0.000)	-	I(1)
INTR	-4.804*** (0.000)	I(0)	-	-4.799*** (0.000)	I(0)	-

Source: Authors' Concept. *** & ** represents 1% and 5% level of significance. (-); represents probability values.

4.4. Long-Run Relationships

Since we have ascertained the existence of cointegration of the variables, we furthered our study by investigating to ascertain if there is an existence of long-run relationships between revenue generation and economic growth in Nigeria or not. The ARDL bounds test, as proposed by Pesaran et al. (2001, 1999), was used for this purpose. It compares the calculated F-statistics with 1% upper critical values. If the F-statistics are greater, there is a long-run relationship between the variables, while if they are lower, there is no relationship. The results of the ARDL bounds test for the specified models are presented in Table 4. From the results, we found that there is existence of long-run relationship between revenue generation and economic growth in Nigeria.

Table 4: ARDL Bound Test

Dep. Var.	F-Stat.	K	Pesaran et al. (2001)						Narayan (2004)					
			1%		5%		10%		1%		5%		10%	
			I(0)	I(1)	I(0)	I(1)	I(0)	I(1)	I(0)	I(1)	I(0)	I(1)	I(0)	I(1)
RGDP	9.582	4	3.74	5.06	2.86	4.01	2.45	3.52	4.59	6.37	3.28	4.63	2.70	3.90

Source: Authors' Concept

4.5. Stability Test

This study further tested the stability of the variables during the study period and for each of the specified models by employing the ARDL recursive CUSUM and CUSUMSQ graphs. The CUSUM and CUSUMSQ tests for parameter stability were first introduced into the statistics and econometrics literature by Brown et al. (1975). The tests aimed at measuring the stability of model variables in the estimated period. The decision rule for the test is that if the bound curve line remains within the 5% critical bounds of the graph, it means that the variables were stable, and if not, the variables were unstable during the period of the study. It was discovered from Fig. 1 below that the variables of the models are stable since the critical lines of both CUSUM and CUSUMSQ graphs lie within the 5% critical bounds of the graphs. This further implied that the model variables are stable in Nigeria in the period covered by this research.

Figure 1: CUSUM and CUSUMSQ Graphs

Source: Authors' Concept

4.6. ARDL Estimation – Baseline Model

In this section, we present and analyze the ARDL results on how revenue generation affects economic growth in Nigeria. Before running the estimations, we ensured that the variables passed key econometric tests, including normality, serial correlation, Ramsey specification, and heteroscedasticity tests, to confirm that the fundamental assumptions of linear models were met. Our findings reveal that past values of economic growth significantly influence current economic growth in Nigeria. Overall, the results indicate that revenue generation has a meaningful impact on economic growth. Specifically, tax revenue (TAX) showed a positive and significant effect of 0.107, suggesting that a one-unit increase in tax revenue boosts economic growth by 0.107 units. On the other hand, value-added tax (VAT) and customs and other import duties (COID) exhibited a significant negative impact of 0.166 and -0.068, respectively indicating that higher value-added tax and import duties may hinder economic growth. We also controlled for inflation (INFR) and interest rates (INTR), both of which showed significant effects on economic growth at varying degrees across the models. In conclusion, while tax revenue positively and significantly drives economic growth, VAT appears to have an insignificant impact, and customs duties negatively influence growth.

In the short run, the error correction model (ECM) coefficients for Models 1 to 3 were negative and statistically significant, indicating adjustment speeds of 1%, 6%, and 28%, respectively, toward long-run equilibrium. Additionally, previous values of economic growth contributed to current growth across the short-run models. Customs duties, inflation, and interest rates also showed significant short-run effects on economic growth. These findings are consistent with prior studies (Garga & Akenegbu, 2022; Amah, 2022; Alao et al., 2023; Asaolu et al., 2018; Onoja & Ibrahim, 2020; Edori, 2022; Abiola et al., 2021), reinforcing the importance of effective revenue management for sustainable economic growth in Nigeria.

Table 7: Estimated Results of ARDL

	Long-Run			Short-Run		
	1	2	3	1	2	3
RGDP (-1)	0.163*** (0.000)	0.588*** (0.014)	-0.471** (0.034)	-0.479*** (0.002)	0.087*** (0.000)	0.084*** (0.000)
TAX	0.107*** (0.007)			0.144 (0.381)		
VAT		-0.261 (0.150)			0.166* (0.084)	
COID			-0.068*** (0.000)			-0.084*** (0.000)
INFR	0.087*** (0.000)	0.077*** (0.000)	0.084*** (0.000)	0.075*** (0.000)	1.397*** (0.001)	1.311*** (0.000)
INTR	-0.056*** (0.003)	0.070*** (0.002)	-0.027 (0.228)	0.051*** (0.009)	-3.650*** (0.000)	-2.881** (0.023)
No of Obs.	12	12	12			
ECM				-0.015*** (0.004)	-0.063** (0.012)	-0.288*** (0.000)
Normality	196.5 (0.000)	563.5 (0.000)	9.909 (0.007)			

Serial Correlation	2.381 (0.213)	3.078 (0.237)	1.156 (0.542)			
Ramsey	-0.194598 (0.0000)	0.389 (0.000)	-0.478 (0.000)			
Heteroscedasticity	0.464 (0.990)	0.961 (0.526)	1.226 (0.212)			

Source: Authors' Concept. ***, ** & *represents 1%, 5% & 10% level of significance. (.) represents probability values.

4.7. Robustness Checks – FMOLS

To address the potential endogeneity issues that the ARDL model cannot fully capture, we applied the fully modified ordinary least squares (FMOLS) method. This approach helps ensure more reliable estimates by accounting for endogeneity. As presented in Table 8, our findings show that past economic growth values significantly influence current growth across all three models. Interestingly, tax revenue (TAX) had a negative and significant effect of -0.093 on economic growth, indicating that an increase in tax revenue could reduce economic growth by 0.093 units. Similarly, value-added tax (VAT) showed a substantial negative impact of -2.935, suggesting that a one-unit rise in VAT could lead to a 2.935-unit decline in economic growth. Customs and other import duties (COID) also displayed a significant negative effect of -0.040, meaning that higher import duties slightly dampen economic growth. When we controlled for key macroeconomic variables — inflation (INFR) and interest rates (INTR) — both variables significantly affected economic growth across the models, though at varying levels. The R-squared results indicated that the variations in economic growth were largely explained by the independent variables, highlighting a good model fit. These findings align with previous studies, including those by Henry (2021), Garga & Akenegbu (2022), Amah (2022), Alao et al. (2023), Asaolu et al. (2018), Onoja & Ibrahim (2020), Edori (2022), and Abiola et al. (2021), reinforcing the importance of understanding how revenue sources and macroeconomic conditions shape Nigeria's economic growth.

Table 8: Estimated FMOLS Results

Variable	FMOLS		
	1	2	3
RGDP (-1)	0.196*** (0.001)	-0.057*** (0.007)	0.045*** (0.000)
TAX	-0.093** (0.022)		
VAT		-2.935*** (0.012)	
COID			-0.040** (0.033)
INFR	0.545*** (0.003)	1.085*** (0.000)	0.231*** (0.000)
INTR	-0.037** (0.023)	-0.202 (0.496)	-0.869*** (0.002)
No of Obs.	12	12	12
R-squared	0.513	0.513	0.712

Source: Authors' Concept. ***, ** & *represents 1%, 5% & 10% level of significance. (.) represents probability values

4.8. Discussion of Findings

This study examines how revenue generation impacts economic growth in Nigeria from 2010 to 2022. Using annual time series data from the World Bank's *World Development Indicators (WDI)*, we explored how key revenue sources influence the country's economic performance. Our primary model was the panel autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model, ideal for capturing both short-term and long-term effects. To ensure robust and reliable results, we also applied the fully modified ordinary least squares (FMOLS) model, which accounts for potential endogeneity, serial correlation, and omitted variable bias.

We measured economic growth using real gross domestic product (GDP) and assessed revenue generation through three main indicators — tax revenue, value-added tax (VAT), and customs and other import duties (COID). Additionally, we controlled for inflation rate (INFR) and interest rate (INTR) to capture the broader macroeconomic environment. This approach provided a comprehensive view of how these factors interact to influence economic growth in Nigeria. By comparing results from both ARDL and FMOLS models, our findings offer deeper insights into the complex relationship between revenue generation and economic performance, helping to inform better fiscal policies aimed at promoting sustainable economic growth.

The ARDL model results revealed mixed effects of revenue sources on Nigeria's economic growth. Tax revenue showed a positive and significant impact, indicating that higher tax collections boost economic performance. A unit increase in tax revenue corresponded to a measurable rise in GDP, reflecting the government's ability to channel tax income into productive investments that drive growth. In contrast, value-added tax (VAT) had an insignificant impact on economic growth. This could be due to inefficiencies in VAT collection or its regressive nature, which disproportionately affects low-income households without significantly contributing to economic output. Such a scenario suggests the need for better VAT administration and more equitable tax policies. On the other hand, customs and other import duties (COID) had a significant negative effect on economic growth. High import duties may raise production costs, discourage trade, and reduce the competitiveness of domestic industries, ultimately slowing economic performance. This finding underscores the importance of balancing trade policies to avoid unintended economic constraints. Overall, the results highlight the need for a more efficient and balanced revenue generation strategy to sustain economic growth in Nigeria.

To reinforce our findings, we employed the FMOLS model, known for addressing endogeneity and measurement errors. Interestingly, the FMOLS results showed that tax revenue, VAT, and customs and other import duties (COID) all had significant negative effects on economic growth. This finding contrasts with the ARDL results, where tax revenue had a positive impact. The negative relationship in the FMOLS model suggests that Nigeria's revenue generation mechanisms may be undermined by structural economic weaknesses, policy inefficiencies, or macroeconomic instability. Persistent inflation, high-interest rates, and exchange rate volatility likely erode the potential gains from revenue collection.

This study aimed to answer three key questions: (a) Does tax revenue significantly impact economic growth in Nigeria? (b) What are the effects of value-added tax on economic growth? (c) How do customs and other import duties influence economic growth? The ARDL model indicated that tax revenue positively impacts growth, VAT shows no significant effect, and COID has a negative impact. However, the FMOLS model suggests all three revenue streams negatively affect growth, reflecting Nigeria's challenging macroeconomic environment. These findings align with previous studies, including Henry (2021), Garga & Akenegbu (2022), Amah (2022), Alao et al. (2023), Asaolu et al. (2018), and others, highlighting the complexities of revenue generation and economic performance in Nigeria.

Improving revenue generation in Nigeria requires a holistic approach that goes beyond merely increasing collections. Structural tax reforms are crucial to enhancing efficiency and reducing the over-reliance on indirect taxes like VAT, which has shown limited impact on economic growth. Creating a more balanced tax system that emphasizes direct taxes could yield better developmental outcomes. Additionally, lowering customs and import duties or offering targeted exemptions for key industries could stimulate trade and industrial expansion, fostering economic growth. Addressing macroeconomic instability is equally vital.

Stabilizing inflation and interest rates can help preserve the value of revenue generated and improve investor confidence. Moreover, investing in human capital development and infrastructure can enhance the productivity of public spending, ensuring that revenue translates into tangible economic benefits. Ultimately, while generating revenue is essential for financing development, how that revenue is utilized matters even more. Achieving sustainable and inclusive economic growth in Nigeria requires a combination of tax reform, regional economic strategies, environmental sustainability, and strong fiscal governance. By focusing on both revenue collection and effective utilization, Nigeria can build a more resilient and dynamic economy.

5. CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. Conclusion

This study highlights the pivotal role of effective revenue generation in promoting sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. Given the country's historical dependence on oil revenues, diversifying revenue sources is essential for achieving economic stability and long-term growth. Our findings show that strengthening tax administration, promoting non-oil sectors, and fostering public-private partnerships (PPPs) can significantly boost revenue generation, which, in turn, stimulates economic growth. One of the study's key insights is the urgent need to diversify Nigeria's revenue base beyond oil dependency. Promoting sectors such as agriculture, manufacturing, and services can create a more resilient economy. Offering incentives, tax breaks, and favorable policies to businesses in these sectors can encourage growth and drive job creation. For example, agriculture has immense potential to generate substantial revenue if supported with better financing and market access. Similarly, investing in manufacturing and services can expand the country's economic output and improve export earnings. Tax reform is critical for improving the efficiency and effectiveness of revenue

collection. Simplifying tax codes, broadening the tax base, and strengthening the capacity of the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) can improve compliance and reduce tax evasion. Leveraging technology for tax administration can also enhance efficiency.

Digital tools can streamline the tax filing process, improve monitoring, and detect non-compliance. Increasing public awareness about the importance of taxation can further boost voluntary compliance by fostering a sense of civic responsibility among citizens. Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) are the backbone of Nigeria's economy, contributing significantly to job creation and economic growth. However, many SMEs struggle with access to finance and high operating costs. Providing tax incentives, grants, and access to credit can stimulate economic activity and, by extension, enhance revenue generation. Supporting SMEs through favorable policies will not only boost government revenue but also promote inclusive growth by reducing unemployment and poverty. Public-private partnerships (PPPs) offer an innovative approach to funding infrastructure and public services while reducing the financial burden on the government. By encouraging private-sector investment through a clear regulatory framework and attractive incentives, the government can improve service delivery and generate additional revenue. Successful PPPs in sectors such as transportation, energy, and healthcare can significantly enhance economic performance and support sustainable development. With the rapid growth of e-commerce and digital services, Nigeria has a unique opportunity to expand its revenue base by taxing the digital economy.

Developing a robust legal framework that addresses the complexities of taxing online transactions can help the government capture revenue from this growing sector. Policies that ensure fair taxation of digital giants while supporting local digital businesses can create a level playing field and drive economic growth. Macroeconomic instability — characterized by high inflation, fluctuating interest rates, and exchange rate volatility — can undermine the benefits of revenue generation. Stabilizing inflation and interest rates can enhance investor confidence and preserve the value of government revenues. Implementing sound monetary and fiscal policies will help create a stable environment where businesses can thrive, ultimately improving revenue inflows. A skilled and productive workforce is essential for economic growth and sustainable revenue generation. Investing in education, vocational training, and skills development can improve labor productivity and economic output. Government programs that focus on equipping the workforce with market-relevant skills can significantly enhance economic performance and broaden the revenue base. Corruption remains a major challenge to revenue generation and public finance management in Nigeria. Strengthening anti-corruption laws, promoting transparency, and ensuring accountability are essential for improving the efficiency of revenue collection and allocation. A transparent and accountable governance structure will build public trust and ensure that revenues are effectively directed toward critical sectors such as education, healthcare, and infrastructure.

Improving revenue generation in Nigeria requires a multifaceted approach that encompasses tax reform, economic diversification, support for SMEs, public-private partnerships, and tackling corruption. By implementing these strategies, Nigeria can create a more resilient and diversified economy that generates sufficient revenue for sustainable economic growth.

Policymakers must prioritize long-term strategies that not only enhance revenue collection but also ensure its efficient utilization for inclusive development.

5.2. Policy Recommendation

To boost revenue generation and drive sustainable economic growth in Nigeria, a well-rounded approach is essential. Relying too heavily on oil has made the economy vulnerable, so it's time to diversify. Sectors like agriculture, manufacturing, and services have huge potential if supported with the right incentives, tax breaks, and business-friendly policies to encourage investment and job creation. Helping farmers and manufacturers access better financing and markets can also strengthen export earnings and economic resilience. Tax reform is another key piece of the puzzle. Simplifying tax codes, broadening the tax base, and using technology to track compliance can improve efficiency and reduce evasion. At the same time, raising public awareness about the importance of taxes can encourage more people to pay voluntarily. Supporting small and medium enterprises (SMEs) is equally important — offering tax incentives, grants, and easier access to credit can fuel economic activity, reduce unemployment, and promote inclusive growth. Public-private partnerships (PPPs) can help tackle Nigeria's infrastructure challenges without overburdening government finances.

Clear regulations and attractive incentives can draw private investment into critical sectors like transportation, energy, and healthcare, improving service delivery while driving economic growth. With the digital economy booming, Nigeria also has an opportunity to generate revenue by taxing e-commerce and online services fairly, ensuring local businesses thrive alongside global tech giants. Addressing macroeconomic instability is crucial, too. High inflation, fluctuating interest rates, and currency volatility can scare off investors and undermine government revenues. Sound monetary and fiscal policies can create a stable environment where businesses can thrive. Investing in education and skills development is another game-changer — a skilled workforce boosts productivity and economic output. Finally, tackling corruption is non-negotiable. Strengthening anti-corruption laws, promoting transparency, and holding officials accountable will improve how public funds are collected and spent, ensuring critical sectors like healthcare, education, and infrastructure get the support they need. By embracing these strategies, Nigeria can build a resilient, diversified economy that supports long-term growth and improves the lives of its people.

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